

PREPARATION AND IDENTIFICATION OF NANOSIZED NICKEL OXIDE AND ITS USE IN REMOVING CRYSTAL VIOLET DYE IN AQUEOUS SOLUTION

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Abstract: The catalyst was prepared by taking nickel chloride hexahydrate and dissolving it with oxalic acid. Adding it drop by drop for an hour, the precipitate was burned and dried, and thus nickel oxide was prepared in powder form, which is used to remove the (Methyl green) dye from the water surface by adsorption method. The best concentration of the (Methyl green) dye was studied and a calibration curve was made for the group of concentrations (0.001, 0.005, 0.007, 0.008, 0.01). It was found that (0.01 g) is the best concentration of the dye at a wavelength of $\lambda_{max}=695$. The best weight of the catalyst was found and how it affected the dye. Also, the calibration curve was made for the group of concentrations (0.01, 0.1, 0.15) where it was shown that the concentration (0.15g) is also the best weight for the catalyst and the effect of temperature on the adsorption process was studied as the adsorption process is considered to be a heat generator and therefore it is inversely proportional to the temperatures (25C_35C_45C). Keywords: (Nickel chloride hexahydrate_ Preparation of nickel oxide in powder form_ Adsorption process_ Nickel chloride hexahydrate and its dissolution with oxalic_ Removal of (Methyl green) dye on a water surface).

Introduction:

Nanotechnology dates back to scientists and researchers who began exploring the small world since the early twentieth century. In 1959, American physicist Richard Feynman referred to the importance of the nanoworld in his lecture called "There's Room at the Bottom", where he used the term "nano" for the first time.

In the following years, interest in nanotechnology increased with the development of vision and micro processing technologies. In 1981, Japanese physicist Norio Taniguchi proposed the use of nanotechnology to build electronic devices at the size of single molecules, which led to the development of the field of nanoelectronics.

Since then, nanotechnology has witnessed tremendous development in research and industrial applications, leading to significant advances in various fields such as medicine, electronics, energy, and materials. Nanotechnology is a set of techniques used to study and manufacture materials and objects at the nanometer level (one millionth of a millimeter). These techniques include the use of modern tools and techniques such as scanning electron microscopy (SEM), transmission electron microscopy (TEM), atomic-scale controlled manufacturing (ALD), 3D printing, and others.

Nanotechnology enables a better understanding of the unique properties and behaviors of materials at the nanometer level, and enables the development of new applications in various fields such as medicine, electronics, energy, environment, and many other fields. Nanotechnology deals with the studies and applications related to materials and structures with nanoscale dimensions, i.e. structures whose size is in the range of 1 to 100 nanometers. This includes studying the distinctive properties and behaviors of these materials at the nanometer level, and using them in various applications such as medicine, electronics, energy, environment, and materials. Nanotechnology includes a wide range of tools and techniques for preparing, analyzing, characterizing, and developing these nanomaterials, such as scanning electron microscopy (SEM), transmission electron microscopy (TEM), spectroscopy, atomic-scale controlled manufacturing (ALD), 3D printing, and many other advanced technologies.

Nanotechnology and Nano Material:

Nanomaterials are materials with extremely small dimensions and are measured in nanometers (nm). Nanomaterials are characterized by their structural and electrical properties [1]. These materials have a nanostructure that is of great importance because it is a link between large materials and molecules at the atomic level. These materials have several practical industrial and medical applications) by using them in magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) [2][3.]

The properties of materials change as their size approaches the nanoscale and as a percentage, the atoms are prominent on the surface. As for materials larger than one micrometer (1 μ m), the percentage of atoms on the surface is very small compared to the total number of atoms in the material. The properties of nanomaterials exhibit a number of properties related to larger materials. Nanoparticles have a very high surface area to volume ratio [4]. This provides tremendous spreading power, especially in areas with high temperatures. Also, the large surface area to volume ratio reduces the melting temperature of nanoparticles [5]. Nanomaterials are prepared by several methods, including the co-precipitation method, wet chemical routes, solid state reaction method, and sol-gel method. Nanomaterials are classified based on the chemical composition and crystal shapes of the nanomaterials. 221 This classification was confirmed in 2001 by the researcher (V..Skorokhod). The optimal classification of nanomaterials was not achieved by these two researchers, and the reason is that the schemes that were developed did not take into account some structures such as nanotubes and fullerenes. Shortly after, a modified scheme for classifying nanomaterials was developed by the researchers (V.V.Pokropivny) and (V.V.Skorokhod), which was based on the number of dimensions of materials that are on the nanoscale, where these materials were classified as follows[6,7] :

- 1) Zero-dimension of nanomaterial: These are materials whose dimensions (X, Y, Z) are all within the nano range (100) as shown in Figure (1-1). This type of material includes nanoparticles and quantum dots.
 - 2) One-dimensional nanomaterial: One-dimension of nanomaterial: Materials in which two of its dimensions are in the nanoscale while the other dimension exceeds the nanoscale (greater than 100 nanometers (as shown in Figure (1-1)). Examples of this type are nanorods, nanowires, and nanotubes.
- Two-dimension of nanomaterial: This type of nanomaterial has only one dimension in the nanoscale as shown in Figure (1-1). Examples of this type of material are nano films and nano layers. Three-

dimension of nanomaterial are also known as bulk nanomaterials. They include all materials whose dimensions are outside the nanoscale (greater than 1000 as shown in Figure (1-1)). The reason for including them in nanomaterials is because they have a nanocrystalline structure or crystal structure. Nanotechnology has features at the nano scale such as bundles of nanorods or nanowires.

Methods:

First step: Preparation of the catalyst (NiCl₄)

Tools and chemicals:

1. Nickel chloride hexahydrate
2. Oxalic
3. Beakers 2
4. Glass stirrer
5. Balance
6. Watch bottle
7. Thermostat
8. Distilled water
9. Spoon
10. Electric heater
11. Magnetic stirrer
12. Filter paper
13. Funnel
14. Electric oven
15. Dropper

Method of work:

- **0.89**of nickel chloride and **3.801** of oxalic were weighed and nickel chloride was dissolved in 100 ml of distilled water. In the beaker.
- **3.801**of oxalic was dissolved in 100 ml of distilled water in another beaker. A magnetic stirrer was placed in an oxalic beaker placed on a water bath until the solution temperature reached 55°C using a thermometer.
- The dissolved nickel chloride was added drop by drop with stirring to the oxalic for an hour.
- The mixture was then filtered and washed with distilled water. The filter paper was dried at 60°C using an electric oven and burned at 450°C.

The second step (preparation of the maximum concentration of the dye)

*Tools and chemicals

1. Cylinder
2. Distilled water
3. Glass stirrer
4. Balance
5. Watch bottle
6. Five volumetric bottles with a capacity of (25mL)
7. Methyl green dye
8. Baker
9. Spectrophotometry device

Method of work: The stock solution was prepared with a concentration of (0.01). 0.114 of the methyl green dye was weighed and dissolved and placed in a 245ml volumetric bottle and the volume was completed with distilled water. After that, 5 solutions with different concentrations of the prepared stock were prepared.

1. The first solution. 2.5ml of the stock solution with a concentration of (0.001) were taken and placed in a volumetric bottle and the volume was completed with distilled water.

2. The second solution. 12.5ml of the stock solution were taken. Its concentration is (0.005) and the volume is completed with distilled water.
3. The third solution: 17.5 ml of the stock solution was taken. Its concentration is (0.007) and the volume is completed with distilled water.
4. The fourth solution: 20 ml of the stock solution was taken. Its concentration is (0.008) and the volume is completed with distilled water.
5. The fifth solution: 25 ml of the stock solution was taken. Its concentration is (0.01) and the volume is completed with distilled water. Then the prepared solutions were measured with a spectrophotometry device to measure the absorbance of the solutions. At $\lambda_{\max} = 695$ and to find the maximum concentration of the dye.

Tools and chemicals:

1. Five 100ml volumetric bottle
2. Methyl green dye
3. Nickel chloride $\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$
4. Distilled water
5. Glass stirrer * Balance * Watch glass
6. Beaker
7. Water bath
8. Spectrophotometer
9. Five conical flasks

Procedure:

1. Weigh 0.1g of the dye (methyl green) and add it to a volumetric bottle and complete the volume with distilled water. That is, a solution of the dye was prepared

2. 2.5ml of the prepared dye solution was added to five volumetric bottles and complete the volume with distilled water
3. Different weights of the catalyst were taken and added. To the prepared solutions, the weight (0.01g- 0.02g - 0.05 - 0.07g and (0.1g.
4. The solutions were added in. 5 conical flasks and placed in a water bath for an hour, after which the absorbance of each solution was measured.

Results and calculations:

To measure the maximum concentration of the dye (Methyl green)

Five solutions of the dye (Methyl green) were prepared with different concentrations (0.001, 0.005, 0.008, 0.007, 0.01) and the maximum concentration of the dye was calculated at $\lambda_{\max}=695$.

To obtain the volumes of these concentrations, the dilution law was applied, where the concentrations were diluted to 25 ml of distilled water according to the dilution law:

$$M1V1=M2V2$$

$$xV = 25 \times 0.001m \Rightarrow V = 2.5 \text{ ml } 0.01$$

$$0.01 \times V = 25 \times 0.005m \Rightarrow V = 12.5 \text{ ml}$$

$$0.01 \times V = 25 \times 0.007m \Rightarrow V = 17.5\text{ml}$$

$$0.01 \times V = 25 \times 0.008m \Rightarrow V = 20\text{ml}$$

$$0.01 \times V = 25 \times 0.010 \text{ m} \Rightarrow V = 25\text{ml}$$

After that, the absorbance was measured as follows:

Abs.	C
0.067	0.001
0.386	0.005
0.463	0.007
0.630	0.008
0.688	0.010

Then the maximum concentration of the dye was found, which is (0.1) M.

Finding the best weight for the catalyst:

100ppm of green methyl was prepared in 100 ml of water and its weight was found to be 0.1g. It was taken from it in 5 flasks and diluted with distilled water and different weights of the catalyst were added to it (0.01, 0.1, 0.15) then it was placed in a water bath for an hour at 25 degrees and continuous withdrawal of 10 ml for each weight every 15 minutes from each solution after which the solutions were filtered and their absorbance was measured.

	Time(min)		Wt. of the catalyst	
	0	0.01	0.1	0.15
0	1	1	1	1
15	0.366	0.279	0.276	0.276
30	0.359	0.266	0.24	0.24
45	0.329	0.266	0.194	0.194
60	0.369	0.246	0.182	0.182

The best weight for the cofactor was found to be 0.15.

Measuring the best temperature:

1 ppm of the dye was prepared in 100ml of distilled water and placed in four flasks and the best weight of the catalyst (0.15) was added to each solution and placed in a water bath at a temperature of (12, 35, 45) where every 15 minutes the absorbance was read for each temperature and the absorbance was as follows:

Time(min)	25 c°	35 c°	45c°
0	1	1	1
15	0.204	0.236	0.243
30	0.199	0.206	0.225
45	0.186	0.196	0.209
60	0.18	0.188	0.19

Discussion:

First: The bands of the two catalyst molecules (nickel oxide) NiO were studied and characterized in the infrared region, as FT-IR spectroscopy is a useful tool for understanding the functional group of any organic molecule. Metal oxides. NiO generally give absorption bands below 1000 cm^{-1} arising from interatomic vibrations. The peak at (443 cm^{-1}) in the spectrum, which shows the Ni-O bond. It gave clear evidence for the presence of crystalline NiO [43]. The peak at 3433 cm^{-1} in the spectra represents H_2O . The bending vibration H-OH appears at 1653 cm^{-1} . There was no evidence for the presence of free precursor material, nickel octanoate, in the sample. Because the stretching vibrations C=O (Uc=O) and CO-O (Uc-o) disappeared. For the samples prepared in Ar atmosphere, no absorption peak below 1000 cm^{-1} was observed. Therefore, we can say that the FT-IR spectra are consistent with the XRD patterns, indicating that the samples obtained under Ar atmosphere are pure and unoxidized metallic nickel. However, it is clear that the surface of these samples is oxidized due to exposure of the sample to air. After oxidation under air, a new peak appears at about 450 cm^{-1} , which is undoubtedly due to Ni-O stretching. The following figure shows the absorption regions of the NiO compound:

Functional Group	Molecular Motion	Wave number (cm ⁻¹)
حامض الكلوريد	Strech (C-Cl) Stretch (C-O)	550 cm ⁻¹ 918.15 cm ⁻¹
هاليدات الالكيل	Strech (C-I)	489.94 cm ⁻¹
مركبات اروماتيه	Strech (C-H)	~1506-1473cm ⁻¹
الكيتونات الالفاتييه	Strech (C=O)	~1716.70 cm ⁻¹
الاسترات الالفاتييه	Strech (C=O) Stretch (N-O)	~1734 cm ⁻¹ ~1363.72 cm ⁻¹
الاميدات	Bend (N-H)	~1570.11 cm ⁻¹
مركبات النايترو الالفاتييه المتماثله	Strech (N-O)	~1600 cm ⁻¹
مركبات النايترو الاروماتيه	Strech (N-O)	~1550 cm ⁻¹
الاميدات	C=O	~1658-1695 cm ⁻¹
الكيتونات	Strech (C=O)	~1643 cm ⁻¹
مركبات الاروماتيه الحلقيه	C=C	~1589 cm ⁻¹
مركبات النايترو	Strech (N-O)	~1558-1473 cm ⁻¹
Alkenes مركبات	Strech (C=C) C=C	~1610-1637 cm ⁻¹ ~1673 cm ⁻¹
الكحولات الفيولات	Strech (O-H)	~3263-3429 cm ⁻¹
الاميدات	Bend (N-H)	~3477-3522 cm ⁻¹

Second: Discussion of the optimal concentration of the dye, where the optimal concentration of the dye was taken from $\lambda_{MAX} = 695$, and the calibration curve was drawn between the concentrations and the absorbance of the solutions, and it was found that the concentration of (0.01) is the ideal concentration of the dye that was relied upon in our study for the research.

Third: Discussion of the best weight of the catalyst, where we notice that the higher the amount of adsorption, the more the weight of the catalyst increases, as it was found that the adsorption speed increases rapidly and then decreases rapidly when the amount of the catalyst increases, and the reason is that the active sites present in the dye that suffer from adsorption decrease, which leads to a decrease in the amount of adsorption.

Fourth: Discussion of the temperature, where we notice that the amount of dye adsorption decreases with increasing temperatures, and the reason is that the adsorption process is a process that generates temperatures, so it is inversely proportional to temperatures, i.e. the lower the temperature, the more the amount of adsorption increases, and vice versa.

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